

Neutrosophic soft cubic Subalgebras of G-algebras

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Abstract: In this paper, neutrosophic soft cubic G-subalgebra is studied through P-union, P-intersection, R-union and R-intersection etc. furthermore we study the notion of homomorphism on G-algebra with some results.

Keywords: G-algebra, Neutrosophic soft cubic set, Neutrosophic soft cubic G-subalgebra, Homomorphism of neutrosophic soft cubic subalgebra.

1 Introduction

Zadeh was the introducer of the fuzzy set and interval-valued fuzzy theory [2] in 1965. Many researchers afterward followed the notions of Zadeh. The cubic set was defined by Jun et al. [9, 10] They used the notion of cubic sets in group and initiated the idea of cubic subgroups. The algebraic structures like *BCK/BCI*-algebra was introduced by Imai et al. [1] in 1966. This algebra was a field of propositional calculus. Many algebraic structures like *G*-algebra, *BG*-algebra, etc. [19, 4] are structured as an extension of *Q*-algebra. Quadratic *B*-algebra was investigated by Park et al. [22]. Molodstov gave the concept of soft sets [14] in 1999. Cubic soft set with application and subalgebra in *BCK/BCI*-algebra were studied by Muhiuddin et al. [15,16]. Senapati et al. [13] generalized the concept of cubic set to *B*-subalgebra with cubic subalgebra and cubic closed ideals. Subalgebra, ideal are studied with the help of cubic set by Jun et al. [12]. The intuitionistic fuzzy *G*-subalgebra is studied by Jana et al. [18]. *L*-fuzzy *G*-subalgebra was studied by Senapati et al. [7]. As an extension of *B*-algebra, lots of work on *BG*-algebra have been done by the Senapati et al. [8]. The idea of a neutrosophic set which was the extension of intuitionistic fuzzy set theory and neutrosophic probability were introduced by Smarandache [20,21]. The notion of neutrosophic cubic set introduced truth-internal and truth-external were extended by Jun et al. [11] and related properties were also investigated by him. Rosenfeld's fuzzy subgroup with an interval-valued membership function was studied by Biswas [3]. The characteristics of the neutrosophic cubic soft set were studied by Pramanik et al. [5]. Cubic *G*-subalgebra with significant results were investigated by jana et al. [17]. The bipolar fuzzy structure of *BG*-algebra was interrogated by Senapati [6]. Neutrosophic cubic soft expert sets were studied for its applications in games by Gulistan M et al. [23]. Neutrosophic cubic graphs and

find out the applications of neutrosophic cubic graphs in the industry by defining the model which are based on the present time and future predictions was studied by Gulistan M et al. [24]. Complex neutrosophic subsemigroups with the Cartesian product, complex neutrosophic (left, right, interior, ideal, characteristic function and direct product was observed by Gulistan M et al. [25]. Results showed the most preferred and the lowest preferred metrics in order to evaluate the sustainability of the supply chain strategy are studied by Abdel-Basset et al. [26]. Hybrid combination between analytical hierarchical process (AHP) as an MCDM method and neutrosophic theory to successfully detect and handle the uncertainty and inconsistency challenges proposed by Abdel-Basset et al. [27]. In this paper, the notion of neutrosophic soft cubic subalgebras (NSCSU) of G-algebras is introduced. And some relevant properties are studied. This study also discussed the homomorphism of neutrosophic soft cubic subalgebras and several related properties.

2 Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 [13] A nonempty set Y with a constant 0 and a binary operation * is said to be G-algebra if it fulfills these axioms.

- G1: $t_1 * t_1 = 0$.
- G2: $t_1 * (t_1 * t_2) = t_2$, for all $t_1, t_2 \in Y$.

A G-algebra is denoted by $(Y, *, 0)$.

Definition 2.2 [3] A nonempty subset S of G-algebra Y is called a subalgebra of Y if $t_1 * t_2 \in S \forall t_1, t_2 \in S$.

Definition 2.3 [3] Mapping $\tau|Y \rightarrow X$ of G-algebras is called homomorphism if $\tau(t_1 * t_2) = \tau(t_1) * \tau(t_2) \forall t_1, t_2 \in Y$.

Note that if $\tau|Y \rightarrow X$ is a g-homomorphism, then $\tau(0) = 0$.

Definition 2.4 [11] A nonempty set A in Y of the form $A = \{ \langle t_1, \vartheta_A(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in Y \}$, is called fuzzy set, where $\vartheta_A(t_1)$ is called the existence value of t_1 in A and $\vartheta_A(t_1) \in [0,1]$.

For a family $A_i = \{ \langle t_1, \vartheta_{A_i}(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in Y \}$ of fuzzy sets in Y, where $i \in h$ and h is index set, we define the join (\vee) meet (\wedge) operations like this:

$$\bigvee_{i \in h} A_i = (\bigvee_{i \in h} \vartheta_{A_i})(t_1) = \sup\{\vartheta_{A_i} \mid i \in h\},$$

and

$$\bigwedge_{i \in h} A_i = (\bigwedge_{i \in h} \vartheta_{A_i})(t_1) = \inf\{\vartheta_{A_i} \mid i \in h\} \text{ respectively, } \forall t_1 \in Y.$$

Definition 2.5 [11] A nonempty set A over Y of the form $A = \{ \langle t_1, \tilde{\vartheta}_A(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in Y \}$, is called IVFS where $\tilde{\vartheta}_A|Y \rightarrow D[0,1]$, here $D[0,1]$ is the collection of all subintervals of $[0,1]$.

The intervals $\tilde{\vartheta}_A t_1 = [\vartheta_A^-(t_1), \vartheta_A^+(t_1)] \forall t_1 \in Y$ denote the degree of existence of the element t_1 to the set A. Also $\tilde{\vartheta}_A^c = [1 - \vartheta_A^-(t_1), 1 - \vartheta_A^+(t_1)]$ represents the complement of $\tilde{\vartheta}_A$.

For a family $\{A_i \mid i \in k\}$ of IVFSs in Y where h is an index set, the union $G = \bigcup_{i \in h} \tilde{\vartheta}_{A_i}(t_1)$ and the intersection $F = \bigcap_{i \in h} \tilde{\vartheta}_{A_i}(t_1)$ are defined below:

$$G(t_1) = (\bigcup_{i \in h} \tilde{\vartheta}_{A_i})(t_1) = \text{rsup}\{\tilde{\vartheta}_{A_i}(t_1) \mid i \in h\}$$

and

$$F(t_1) = (\bigcap_{i \in h} \tilde{\vartheta}_{A_i})(t_1) = \text{rinf}\{\tilde{\vartheta}_{A_i}(t_1) \mid i \in k\}, \text{ respectively, } \forall t_1 \in Y.$$

Definition 2.6 [12] Consider two elements $K_1, K_2 \in D[0,1]$. If $K_1 = [f_1^-, f_1^+]$ and $K_2 = [f_2^-, f_2^+]$, then $\text{rmax}(K_1, K_2) = [\max(f_1^-, f_2^-), \max(f_1^+, f_2^+)]$ which is denoted by $K_1 \vee^r K_2$ and $\text{rmin}(K_1, K_2) = [\min(f_1^-, f_2^-), \min(f_1^+, f_2^+)]$ which is denoted by $K_1 \wedge^r K_2$. Thus, if $K_i = [f_i^-, f_i^+] \in K[0,1]$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, then we define $\text{rsup}_i(K_i) = [\sup_i(f_i^-), \sup_i(f_i^+)]$, i.e., $\vee_i^r K_i = [\vee_i(f_i^-), \vee_i(f_i^+)]$. Similarly we define $\text{rinf}_i(K_i) = [\inf_i(f_i^-), \inf_i(f_i^+)]$, i.e., $\wedge_i^r K_i = [\wedge_i(f_i^-), \wedge_i(f_i^+)]$. Now $K_1 \geq K_2 \iff f_1^- \geq f_2^-$ and $f_1^+ \geq f_2^+$. Similarly the relations $K_1 \leq K_2$ and $K_1 = K_2$ are defined.

Definition 2.7 [13] A fuzzy set $A = \{ \langle t_1, \vartheta_A(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in Y \}$ is called a fuzzy subalgebra of Y if $\vartheta_A(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{\vartheta_A(t_1), \vartheta_A(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in Y$.

Definition 2.8 [22] A pair $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A, \Lambda)$ is called NCS where $A = \{ \langle t_1; A_T(t_1), A_I(t_1), A_F(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in Y \}$ is an INS in Y and $\Lambda = \{ \langle t_1; \lambda_T(t_1), \lambda_I(t_1), \lambda_F(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in Y \}$ is a neutrosophic set in Y .

Definition 2.9 [3] Let $C = \{ \langle t_1, A(t_1), \lambda(t_1) \rangle \}$ be a cubic set, where $A(t_1)$ is an IVFS in Y , $\lambda(t_1)$ is a fuzzy set in Y and Y is subalgebra. Then A is cubic subalgebra under binary operation $*$ if it fulfills these axioms:

- C1: $A(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{A(t_1), A(t_2)\}$,
- C2: $\lambda(t_1 * t_2) \leq \text{max}\{\lambda(t_1), \lambda(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in Y$.

Definition 3.0 [14] Let U be an universe set. Let $NC(U)$ represents the set of all neutrosophic cubic sets and E be the collection of parameters. Let $K \subset E$ then $\tilde{P}_K = \{ \langle t_1, A_{e_i}(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in U, e_i \in K \}$, where $A_{e_i}(t_1) = \{ \langle A_{e_i}^T(t_1), (A_{e_i}^I)_{e_i}(t_1), (A_{e_i}^F)_{e_i}(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in U \}$, is an interval neutrosophic soft set, $\lambda_{e_i}(t_1) = \{ \langle \lambda_{e_i}^T(t_1), (A_{e_i}^I)_{e_i}(t_1), (\lambda_{e_i}^F)_{e_i}(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in U \}$ is a neutrosophic soft set. \tilde{P}_K is named as the neutrosophic soft cubic set over U where \tilde{P} is a mapping given by $\tilde{P} \mid K \rightarrow NC(U)$. The sets of all neutrosophic soft cubic sets over U will be denoted by C_U^N .

3 Neutrosophic Soft Cubic Subalgebras of G-Algebra

Definition 3.1 Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}, \Lambda_{e_i})$ be a neutrosophic soft cubic set, where Y is subalgebra. Then $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is NSCSU under binary operation $*$ if it holds the following conditions:

- N1:
 - $A_{e_i}^T(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^T(t_1), A_{e_i}^T(t_2)\}$
 - $A_{e_i}^I(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^I(t_1), A_{e_i}^I(t_2)\}$
 - $A_{e_i}^F(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^F(t_1), A_{e_i}^F(t_2)\}$,
- N2:
 - $\Lambda_{e_i}^T(t_1 * t_2) \leq \text{max}\{\Lambda_{e_i}^T(t_1), \Lambda_{e_i}^T(t_2)\}$
 - $\Lambda_{e_i}^I(t_1 * t_2) \leq \text{max}\{\Lambda_{e_i}^I(t_1), \Lambda_{e_i}^I(t_2)\}$
 - $\Lambda_{e_i}^F(t_1 * t_2) \leq \text{max}\{\Lambda_{e_i}^F(t_1), \Lambda_{e_i}^F(t_2)\}$.

For simplicity we introduced new notation for neutrosophic soft cubic set as

$$\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^{T,I,F}, \lambda_{e_i}^{T,I,F}) = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o) = \{ \langle t_1, A_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1) \rangle \}$$

and for conditions N1, N2 as

- N1: $A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$,
- N2: $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \leq \text{max}\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$.

Example 3.2 Let $Y = \{0, c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5\}$ be a G-algebra with the following Cayley table.

*	0	c ₁	c ₂	c ₃	c ₄	c ₅
0	0	c ₅	c ₄	c ₃	c ₂	c ₁
c ₁	c ₁	0	c ₅	c ₄	c ₃	c ₂
c ₂	c ₂	c ₁	0	c ₅	c ₄	c ₃
c ₃	c ₃	c ₂	c ₁	0	c ₅	c ₄
c ₄	c ₄	c ₃	c ₂	c ₁	0	c ₅
c ₅	c ₅	c ₄	c ₃	c ₂	c ₁	0

A NSCS $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^q, \lambda_{e_i}^q)$ of Y is defined by

*	0	c ₁	c ₂	c ₃	c ₄	c ₅
A ^T _{e_i}	[0.6,0.8]	[0.5,0.7]	[0.6,0.8]	[0.5,0.7]	[0.6,0.8]	[0.5,0.7]
A ^I _{e_i}	[0.5,0.4]	[0.4,0.3]	[0.5,0.4]	[0.4,0.3]	[0.5,0.4]	[0.4,0.3]
A ^F _{e_i}	[0.5,0.7]	[0.3,0.6]	[0.5,0.7]	[0.3,0.6]	[0.5,0.7]	[0.3,0.6],

and

*	0	c ₁	c ₂	c ₃	c ₄	c ₅
λ ^T _{e_i}	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.5
λ ^I _{e_i}	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.7
λ ^F _{e_i}	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.8.

Definition 3.1 is satisfied by the set $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$. Thus $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^q, \lambda_{e_i}^q)$ is a NSCSU of Y .

Proposition 3.3 Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = \{(t_1, A_{e_i}^q(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1))\}$ is a NSCSU of Y , then $\forall t_1 \in Y, A_{e_i}^q(t_1) \geq A_{e_i}^q(0)$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^q(0) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1)$. Thus, $A_{e_i}^q(0)$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^q(0)$ are the upper bounds and lower bounds of $A_{e_i}^q(t_1)$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1)$ respectively.

Proof. For all $t_1 \in Y$, we have $A_{e_i}^q(0) = A_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_1) \geq \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^q(t_1), A_{e_i}^q(t_1)\} = A_{e_i}^q(t_1) \Rightarrow A_{e_i}^q(0) \geq A_{e_i}^q(t_1)$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^q(0) = \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_1) \leq \max\{\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1)\} = \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1) \Rightarrow \lambda_{e_i}^q(0) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1)$.

Theorem 3.4 Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = \{(t_1, A_{e_i}^q(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1))\}$ be a NSCSU of Y . If there exists a sequence $\{(t_1)_n\}$ of Y such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} A_{e_i}^q((t_1)_n) = [1,1]$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \lambda_{e_i}^q((t_1)_n) = 0$. Then $A_{e_i}^q(0) = [1,1]$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^q(0) = 0$.

Proof. Using Proposition 3.3, $A_{e_i}^q(0) \geq A_{e_i}^q(t_1) \forall t_1 \in Y, \therefore A_{e_i}^q(0) \geq A_{e_i}^q((t_1)_n)$ for $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Consider, $[1,1] \geq A_{e_i}^q(0) \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} A_{e_i}^q((t_1)_n) = [1,1]$. Hence, $A_{e_i}^q(0) = [1,1]$. Again, using Proposition 3.3, $\lambda_{e_i}^q(0) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1) \forall t_1 \in Y, \therefore \lambda_{e_i}^q(0) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^q((t_1)_n)$ for $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Consider, $0 \leq \lambda_{e_i}^q(0) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \lambda_{e_i}^q((t_1)_n) = 0$. Hence, $\lambda_{e_i}^q(0) = 0$.

Theorem 3.5 The R-intersection of any set of NSCSU of Y is also a NSCSU of Y .

Proof. Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = \{(t_1, A_{e_i}^q, \lambda_{e_i}^q) | t_1 \in Y\}$ where $i \in k$, be set of NSCSU of Y and $t_1, t_2 \in Y$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (\cap A_{e_i}^q)(t_1 * t_2) &= \text{rinf} A_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_2) \\ &\geq \text{rinf}\{\text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^q(t_1), A_{e_i}^q(t_2)\}\} \\ &= \text{rmin}\{\text{rinf} A_{e_i}^q(t_1), \text{rinf} A_{e_i}^q(t_2)\} \\ &= \text{rmin}\{(\cap A_{e_i}^q)(t_1), (\cap A_{e_i}^q)(t_2)\} \\ &\Rightarrow (\cap A_{e_i}^q)(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{(\cap A_{e_i}^q)(t_1), (\cap A_{e_i}^q)(t_2)\} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} (\vee \lambda_{e_i}^q)(t_1 * t_2) &= \text{sup} \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_2) \\ &\leq \text{sup}\{\max\{\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_2)\}\} \\ &= \max\{\text{sup} \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1), \text{sup} \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_2)\} \\ &= \max\{(\vee \lambda_{e_i}^q)(t_1), (\vee \lambda_{e_i}^q)(t_2)\} \\ &\Rightarrow (\vee \lambda_{e_i}^q)(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{(\vee \lambda_{e_i}^q)(t_1), (\vee \lambda_{e_i}^q)(t_2)\}, \end{aligned}$$

which show that R-intersection of $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is a NSCSU of Y.

Remark 3.6 This is not compulsory that R-union, P-intersection and P-union of NSCSU are also the NSCSU.

Example 3.7 Let $Y = \{0, c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5\}$ be a G-algebra with the following Cayley table.

*	0	c_1	c_2	c_3	c_4	c_5
0	0	c_2	c_1	c_3	c_4	c_5
c_1	c_1	0	c_2	c_5	c_3	c_4
c_2	c_2	c_1	0	c_4	c_5	c_3
c_3	c_3	c_4	c_5	0	c_1	c_2
c_4	c_4	c_5	c_3	c_2	0	c_1
c_5	c_5	c_3	c_4	c_1	c_2	0.

Let $\mathcal{A}_{e_1} = (A_{e_1}^e, \lambda_{e_1}^e)$ and $\mathcal{A}_{e_2} = (A_{e_2}^e, \lambda_{e_2}^e)$ are neutrosophic soft cubic sets of Y defined by

	0	c_1	c_2	c_3	c_4	c_5
$A_{e_1}T$	[0.5,0.4]	[0.1,0.2]	[0.1,0.2]	[0.5,0.4]	[0.1,0.2]	[0.1,0.2]
$A_{e_1}I$	[0.6,0.7]	[0.2,0.3]	[0.2,0.3]	[0.6,0.7]	[0.2,0.3]	[0.2,0.3]
$A_{e_1}F$	[0.7,0.8]	[0.3,0.4]	[0.3,0.4]	[0.7,0.8]	[0.3,0.4]	[0.3,0.4]
$A_{e_2}T$	[0.6,0.7]	[0.2,0.3]	[0.2,0.3]	[0.6,0.7]	[0.2,0.3]	[0.2,0.3]
$A_{e_2}I$	[0.5,0.4]	[0.1,0.2]	[0.1,0.2]	[0.1,0.2]	[0.5,0.4]	[0.1,0.2]
$A_{e_2}F$	[0.4,0.3]	[0.2,0.4]	[0.2,0.4]	[0.2,0.4]	[0.4,0.5]	[0.2,0.4]

and

	0	c_1	c_2	c_3	c_4	c_5
$\lambda_{e_1}T$	0.2	0.8	0.8	0.3	0.8	0.8
$\lambda_{e_1}I$	0.3	0.7	0.7	0.4	0.7	0.7
$\lambda_{e_1}F$	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.6
$\lambda_{e_2}T$	0.3	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.5
$\lambda_{e_2}I$	0.4	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.5	0.7
$\lambda_{e_2}F$	0.5	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.6	0.9

Then \mathcal{A}_{e_1} and \mathcal{A}_{e_2} are neutrosophic soft cubic subalgebras of Y but R-union, P-union and P-intersection of \mathcal{A}_{e_1} and \mathcal{A}_{e_2} are not neutrosophic soft cubic subalgebras of Y. $(\cup A_{e_1}^e)(c_3 * c_4) = ([0.2,0.5], [0.2,0.3], [0.3,0.4])_q = \text{rmin}\{(U A_{e_1}^e)(c_3), (U A_{e_1}^e)(c_4)\}$ and $(\wedge \lambda_{e_1}^e)(c_3 * c_4) = (0.7,0.6,0.8)_q \not\subseteq (0.1,0.2,0.3)_q = \text{max}\{(\wedge \lambda_{e_1}^e)(c_3), (\wedge \lambda_{e_1}^e)(c_4)\}$.

We give the conditions that R-union, P-union and P-intersection of NSCSU are also NSCSU. Which are at Theorem 3.8, 3.9, 3.10.

Theorem 3.8 Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = \{(t_1, A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o) | t_1 \in Y\}$ where $i \in k$ be set of NSCSU of Y , where $i \in k$. If $\inf\{\max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}\} = \max\{\inf\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \inf\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in Y$. Then the P-intersection of $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is also a NSCSU of Y .

Proof. Suppose that $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = \{(t_1, A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o) | t_1 \in Y\}$ where $i \in k$ be set of NSCSU of Y such that $\inf\{\max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}\} = \max\{\inf\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \inf\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in Y$. Then for $t_1, t_2 \in Y$. Then $(\cap A_{e_i}^o)(t_1 * t_2) = \text{rinf}A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rinf}\{\text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}\} = \text{rmin}\{\text{rinf}A_{e_i}^o(t_1), \text{rinf}A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} = \text{rmin}\{(\cap A_{e_i}^o)(t_1), (\cap A_{e_i}^o)(t_2)\} \Rightarrow (\cap A_{e_i}^o)(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{(\cap A_{e_i}^o)(t_1), (\cap A_{e_i}^o)(t_2)\}$ and $(\wedge \lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_1 * t_2) = \inf\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \leq \inf\{\max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}\} = \max\{\inf\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \inf\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} = \max\{(\wedge \lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_1), (\wedge \lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_2)\} \Rightarrow (\wedge \lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{(\wedge \lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_1), (\wedge \lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_2)\}$, which show that P - intersection of $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is a NSCSU of Y .

Theorem 3.9 Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = \{(t_1, A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o) | t_1 \in Y\}$ where $i \in k$ be set of NSCSU of Y . If $\sup\{\text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}\} = \text{rmin}\{\sup A_{e_i}^o(t_1), \sup A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in Y$. Then the P-union of $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is also a NSCSU of Y .

Proof. Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = \{(t_1, A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o) | t_1 \in Y\}$ where $i \in k$ be set of NSCSU of Y such that $\sup\{\text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}\} = \text{rmin}\{\sup A_{e_i}^o(t_1), \sup A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in Y$. Then for $t_1, t_2 \in Y, (U A_{e_i}^o)(t_1 * t_2) = \text{rsup}A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rsup}\{\text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}\} = \text{rmin}\{\text{rsup}A_{e_i}^o(t_1), \text{rsup}A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} = \text{rmin}\{(U A_{e_i}^o)(t_1), (U A_{e_i}^o)(t_2)\} \Rightarrow (U A_{e_i}^o)(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{(U A_{e_i}^o)(t_1), (U A_{e_i}^o)(t_2)\}$

an $(\vee \lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_1 * t_2) = \sup\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \leq \sup\{\max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}\} = \max\{\sup\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \sup\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} = \max\{(\vee \lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_1), (\vee \lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_2)\} \Rightarrow (\vee \lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{(\vee \lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_1), (\vee \lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_2)\}$, which show that P-union of $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is a NSCSU of Y .

Theorem 3.10 Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = \{(t_1, A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o) | t_1 \in Y\}$ where $i \in k$ be set of NSCSU of Y . If $\inf\{\max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}\} = \max\{\inf\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \inf\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$ and $\sup\{\text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}\} = \text{rmin}\{\sup A_{e_i}^o(t_1), \sup A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in Y$. Then the R-union of $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is also a NSCSU of Y .

Proof. Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = \{(t_1, A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o) | t_1 \in Y\}$ where $i \in k$ be set of NSCSU of Y such that $\inf\{\max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}\} = \max\{\inf\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \inf\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$ and $\sup\{\text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}\} = \text{rmin}\{\sup A_{e_i}^o(t_1), \sup A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in Y$. Then for $t_1, t_2 \in Y, (U A_{e_i}^o)(t_1 * t_2) = \text{rsup}A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rsup}\{\text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}\} = \text{rmin}\{\text{rsup}A_{e_i}^o(t_1), \text{rsup}A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} = \text{rmin}\{(U A_{e_i}^o)(t_1), (U A_{e_i}^o)(t_2)\} \Rightarrow (U A_{e_i}^o)(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{(U A_{e_i}^o)(t_1), (U A_{e_i}^o)(t_2)\}$ and $(\wedge \lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_1 * t_2) = \inf\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \leq \inf\{\max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}\} = \max\{\inf\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \inf\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} = \max\{(\wedge \lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_1), (\wedge \lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_2)\} \Rightarrow (\wedge \lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{(\wedge \lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_1), (\wedge \lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_2)\}$, which show that R-union of $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is a NSCSU of Y .

Proposition 3.11 If a neutrosophic soft cubic set $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ of Y is a subalgebra. Then $\forall t_1 \in Y, A_{e_i}^o(0 * t_1) \geq A_{e_i}^o(t_1)$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o(0 * t_1) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1)$.

Proof. For all $t_1 \in Y$, $A_{e_i}^o(0 * t_1) \geq \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(0), A_{e_i}^o(t_1)\} = \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_1)\} \geq \text{rmin}\{\text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_1)\}, A_{e_i}^o(t_1)\} = A_{e_i}^o(t_1)$ and similarly $\lambda_{e_i}^o(0 * t_1) \leq \text{max}\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(0), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1)\} = \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1)$.

Lemma 3.12 If a neutrosophic soft cubic set $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ of Y is a subalgebra. Then $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k(t_1 * t_2) = \tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k(t_1 * (0 * (0 * t_2))) \forall t_1, t_2 \in Y$.

Proof. Let Y be a G -algebra and $t_1, t_2 \in Y$. Then $t_2 = 0 * (0 * t_2)$ by ([9], Lemma 3.1). Hence $A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) = A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * (0 * (0 * t_2)))$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) = \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * (0 * (0 * t_2)))$. Therefore, $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k(t_1 * t_2) = \tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k(t_1 * (0 * (0 * t_2)))$

Proposition 3.13 If a NSCS $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ of Y is NSCSU. Then $\forall t_1, t_2 \in Y$, $A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * (0 * t_2)) \geq \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * (0 * t_2)) \leq \text{max}\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$.

Proof. Let $t_1, t_2 \in Y$. Then we have $A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * (0 * t_2)) \geq \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(0 * t_2)\} \geq \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * (0 * t_2)) \leq \text{max}\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(0 * t_2)\} \leq \text{max}\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$ by Definition 3.1 and Proposition 3.11. Hence proof is completed.

Theorem 3.14 If a NSCS $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ of Y satisfies the following conditions. Then $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ refers to a NSCSU of Y .

1. $A_{e_i}^o(0 * t_1) \geq A_{e_i}^o(t_1)$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o(0 * t_1) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^o(x) \forall t_1 \in Y$.
2. $A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * (0 * t_2)) \geq \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * (0 * t_2)) \leq \text{max}\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in Y$.

Proof. Assume that the neutrosophic soft cubic set $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ of Y satisfies the above conditions. Then by Lemma 3.12, $A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) = A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * (0 * (0 * t_2))) \geq \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(0 * t_2)\} \geq \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) = \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * (0 * (0 * t_2))) \leq \text{max}\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(0 * t_2)\} \leq \text{max}\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in Y$. Hence $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is NSCSU of Y .

Theorem 3.15 A neutrosophic soft cubic set $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ of Y is NSCSU of Y iff $(A_{e_i}^o)^-, (A_{e_i}^o)^+$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o$ are fuzzy subalgebras of Y .

Proof. Let $(A_{e_i}^o)^-, (A_{e_i}^o)^+$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o$ are fuzzy subalgebra of Y and $t_1, t_2 \in Y$ then $(A_{e_i}^o)^-(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{min}\{(A_{e_i}^o)^-(t_1), (A_{e_i}^o)^-(t_2)\}$, $(A_{e_i}^o)^+(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{min}\{(A_{e_i}^o)^+(t_1), (A_{e_i}^o)^+(t_2)\}$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \leq \text{max}\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$. Now, $A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) = [(A_{e_i}^o)^-(t_1 * t_2), (A_{e_i}^o)^+(t_1 * t_2)] \geq [\text{min}\{(A_{e_i}^o)^-(t_1), (A_{e_i}^o)^-(t_2)\}, \text{min}\{(A_{e_i}^o)^+(t_1), (A_{e_i}^o)^+(t_2)\}] \geq \text{rmin}\{[(A_{e_i}^o)^-(t_1), (A_{e_i}^o)^+(t_1)], [(A_{e_i}^o)^-(t_2), (A_{e_i}^o)^+(t_2)]\} = \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$. Therefore, $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is NSCSU of Y .

Conversely, assume that $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is a NSCSU of Y . For any $t_1, t_2 \in Y$, $[(A_{e_i}^o)^-(t_1 * t_2), (A_{e_i}^o)^+(t_1 * t_2)] = A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} = \text{rmin}\{[(A_{e_i}^o)^-(t_1), (A_{e_i}^o)^+(t_1)], [(A_{e_i}^o)^-(t_2), (A_{e_i}^o)^+(t_2)]\} = [\text{min}\{(A_{e_i}^o)^-(t_1), (A_{e_i}^o)^-(t_2)\}, \text{min}\{(A_{e_i}^o)^+(t_1), (A_{e_i}^o)^+(t_2)\}]$. Thus, $(A_{e_i}^o)^-(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{min}\{(A_{e_i}^o)^-(t_1), (A_{e_i}^o)^-(t_2)\}$, $(A_{e_i}^o)^+(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{min}\{(A_{e_i}^o)^+(t_1), (A_{e_i}^o)^+(t_2)\}$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \leq \text{max}\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$. Thus, $(A_{e_i}^o)^-, (A_{e_i}^o)^+$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o$ are fuzzy subalgebras of Y .

$t_2) \geq \min\{(A_{e_i}^q)^-(t_1), (A_{e_i}^q)^-(t_2)\}$, $(A_{e_i}^q)^+(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{(A_{e_i}^q)^+(t_1), (A_{e_i}^q)^+(t_2)\}$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_2)\}$. Hence $(A_{e_i}^q)^-$, $(A_{e_i}^q)^+$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^q$ are fuzzy subalgebras of Y .

Theorem 3.16 Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^q, \lambda_{e_i}^q)$ be a NSCSU of Y and let $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Then

- i) $A_{e_i}^q(\coprod n t_1 * t_1) \geq A_{e_i}^q(t_1)$ for $n \in \mathbb{O}$.
- ii) $\lambda_{e_i}^q(\coprod n t_1 * t_1) \leq A_{e_i}^q(t_1)$ for $n \in \mathbb{O}$.
- iii) $A_{e_i}^q(\coprod n t_1 * t_1) = A_{e_i}^q(t_1)$ for $n \in \mathbb{E}$.
- iv) $\lambda_{e_i}^q(\coprod n t_1 * t_1) = A_{e_i}^q(t_1)$ for $n \in \mathbb{E}$.

Proof. Let $t_1 \in Y$ and suppose that n is odd. Then $n = 2p - 1$ for some $p \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. We prove the theorem by induction.

Now $A_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_1) = A_{e_i}^q(0) \geq A_{e_i}^q(t_1)$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_1) = \lambda_{e_i}^q(0) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1)$. Suppose that $A_{e_i}^q(\coprod_{2p-1} t_1 * t_1) \geq A_{e_i}^q(t_1)$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^q(\coprod_{2p-1} t_1 * t_1) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1)$. Then by assumption, $A_{e_i}^q(\coprod_{2(p+1)-1} t_1 * t_1) = A_{e_i}^q(\coprod_{2p+1} t_1 * t_1) = A_{e_i}^q(\coprod_{2p-1} t_1 * (t_1 * t_1)) = A_{e_i}^q(\coprod_{2p-1} t_1 * t_1) \geq A_{e_i}^q(t_1)$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^q(\coprod_{2(p+1)-1} t_1 * t_1) = \lambda_{e_i}^q(\coprod_{2p+1} t_1 * t_1) = \lambda_{e_i}^q(\coprod_{2p-1} t_1 * (t_1 * t_1)) = \lambda_{e_i}^q(\coprod_{2p-1} t_1 * t_1) \leq \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1)$, which proves (1) and (2). Similarly, cases (3) and (4) has the same proofs.

These sets denoted by $I_{A_{e_i}^q}$ and $I_{\lambda_{e_i}^q}$ are subalgebras of Y . Which were defined as

$$I_{A_{e_i}^q} = \{t_1 \in Y | A_{e_i}^q(t_1) = A_{e_i}^q(0)\}, I_{\lambda_{e_i}^q} = \{t_1 \in Y | \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1) = \lambda_{e_i}^q(0)\}.$$

Theorem 3.17 Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^q, \lambda_{e_i}^q)$ be a NSCSU of Y . Then the sets $I_{A_{e_i}^q}$ and $I_{\lambda_{e_i}^q}$ are subalgebras of Y .

Proof. Let $t_1, t_2 \in I_{A_{e_i}^q}$. Then $A_{e_i}^q(t_1) = A_{e_i}^q(0) = A_{e_i}^q(t_2)$ and so, $A_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{A_{e_i}^q(t_1), A_{e_i}^q(t_2)\} = A_{e_i}^q(0)$. By using Proposition 3.3, we know that $A_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_2) = A_{e_i}^q(0)$ or equivalently $t_1 * t_2 \in I_{A_{e_i}^q}$.

Again suppose $t_1, t_2 \in I_{\lambda_{e_i}^q}$. Then $\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1) = \lambda_{e_i}^q(0) = \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_2)$ and so, $\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_2)\} = \lambda_{e_i}^q(0)$. Again by using Proposition 3.3, we know that $\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_2) = \lambda_{e_i}^q(0)$ or equivalently $t_1 * t_2 \in I_{\lambda_{e_i}^q}$. Hence the sets $I_{A_{e_i}^q}$ and $I_{\lambda_{e_i}^q}$ are subalgebras of Y .

Theorem 3.18 Assume B is a nonempty subset of Y and $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^q, \lambda_{e_i}^q)$ be a neutrosophic soft cubic set of Y defined by

$$A_{e_i}^q(t_1) = \begin{cases} [\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}], & \text{if } t_1 \in B \\ [\beta_{T,I,F_1}, \beta_{T,I,F_2}], & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \Lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1) = \begin{cases} \gamma_q, & \text{if } t_1 \in B \\ \delta_q, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

$\forall [\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}], [\beta_{T,I,F_1}, \beta_{T,I,F_2}] \in D[0,1]$ and $\gamma_q, \delta_q \in [0,1]$ with $[\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}] \geq [\beta_{T,I,F_1}, \beta_{T,I,F_2}]$ and $\gamma_q \leq \delta_q$. Then $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is a neutrosophic soft cubic subalgebra of $Y \Leftarrow B$ is a subalgebra of Y . Moreover,

$$I_{A_{e_i}^q} = B = I_{\lambda_{e_i}^q}.$$

Proof. Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ be a NSCSU of Y . Let $t_1, t_2 \in Y$ such that $t_1, t_2 \in B$. Then $A_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{A_{e_i}^q(t_1), A_{e_i}^q(t_2)\} = \min\{[\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}], [\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}]\} = [\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}]$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_2)\} = \max\{\gamma_q, \gamma_q\} = \gamma_q$. Therefore $t_1 * t_2 \in B$. Hence, B is a subalgebra of Y .

Conversely, assume that B is a subalgebra of Y . Let $t_1, t_2 \in Y$. Now take two cases.

Case 1: If $t_1, t_2 \in B$, then $t_1 * t_2 \in B$, thus $A_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_2) = [\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}] = \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^q(t_1), A_{e_i}^q(t_2)\}$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_2) = \gamma_q = \max\{\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_2)\}$.

Case 2: If $t_1 \notin B$ or $t_2 \notin B$, then $A_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_2) \geq [\beta_{T,I,F_1}, \beta_{T,I,F_2}] = \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^q(t_1), A_{e_i}^q(t_2)\}$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_2) \leq \delta_q = \max\{\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_2)\}$. Hence $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is a NSCSU of Y .

Now, $I_{A_{e_i}^q} = \{t_1 \in Y, A_{e_i}^q(t_1) = A_{e_i}^q(0)\} = \{t_1 \in Y, A_{e_i}^q(t_1) = [\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}]\} = B$ and $I_{\lambda_{e_i}^q} = \{t_1 \in Y, \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1) = \lambda_{e_i}^q(0)\} = \{t_1 \in Y, \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1) = \gamma_q\} = B$.

Definition 3.19 Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^q, \lambda_{e_i}^q)$ be a neutrosophic soft cubic set of Y . For $[w_{T_1}, w_{T_2}], [w_{I_1}, w_{I_2}], [w_{F_1}, w_{F_2}] \in D[0,1]$ and $t_{T_1}, t_{I_1}, t_{F_1} \in [0,1]$, the set $U(A_{e_i}^q | ([w_{T_1}, w_{T_2}], [w_{I_1}, w_{I_2}], [w_{F_1}, w_{F_2}])) = \{t_1 \in Y | A_{e_i}^T(t_1) \geq [w_{T_1}, w_{T_2}], A_{e_i}^I(t_1) \geq [w_{I_1}, w_{I_2}], A_{e_i}^F(t_1) \geq [w_{F_1}, w_{F_2}]\}$ is called upper $([w_{T_1}, w_{T_2}], [w_{I_1}, w_{I_2}], [w_{F_1}, w_{F_2}])$ -level of $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ and $L(\lambda_{e_i}^q | (t_{T_1}, t_{I_1}, t_{F_1})) = \{t_1 \in Y | \Lambda_{e_i}^T(t_1) \leq t_{T_1}, \Lambda_{e_i}^I(t_1) \leq t_{I_1}, \Lambda_{e_i}^F(t_1) \leq t_{F_1}\}$ is called lower $(t_{T_1}, t_{I_1}, t_{F_1})$ -level of $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$.

For convenience, we introduced the new notions for upper level and lower level of $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ as, $U(A_{e_i}^q | [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}]) = \{t_1 \in Y | A_{e_i}^q(t_1) \geq [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}]\}$ is called upper $([w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}])$ -level of $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ and $L(\lambda_{e_i}^q | t_{T,I,F_1}) = \{t_1 \in Y | \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1) \leq t_{T,I,F_1}\}$ is called lower t_{T,I,F_1} -level of $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$.

Theorem 3.20 If $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^q, \lambda_{e_i}^q)$ is neutrosophic soft cubic subalgebra of Y , then the upper $[w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}]$ -level and lower t_{T,I,F_1} -level of $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ are subalgebras of Y .

Proof. Let $t_1, t_2 \in U(A_{e_i}^q | [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}])$. Then $A_{e_i}^q(t_1) \geq [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}]$ and $A_{e_i}^q(t_2) \geq [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}]$. It follows that $A_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^q(t_1), A_{e_i}^q(t_2)\} \geq [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}] \Rightarrow t_1 * t_2 \in U(A_{e_i}^q | [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}])$. Hence, $U(A_{e_i}^q | [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}])$ is a subalgebra of Y .

Let $t_1, t_2 \in L(\lambda_{e_i}^q | t_{T,I,F_1})$. Then $\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1) \leq t_{T,I,F_1}$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_2) \leq t_{T,I,F_1}$. It follows that $\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_2)\} \leq t_{T,I,F_1} \Rightarrow t_1 * t_2 \in L(\lambda_{e_i}^q | t_{T,I,F_1})$. Hence $L(\lambda_{e_i}^q | t_{T,I,F_1})$ is a subalgebra of Y .

Corollary 3.21 Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^q, \lambda_{e_i}^q)$ is NSCSU of Y . Then $A([w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}], t_{T,I,F_1}) = U(A_{e_i}^q | [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}]) \cap L(\lambda_{e_i}^q | t_{T,I,F_1}) = \{t_1 \in Y | A_{e_i}^q(t_1) \geq [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}], \lambda_{e_i}^q(t_1) \leq t_{T,I,F_1}\}$ is a subalgebra of Y .

Proof. We can prove it by using Theorem 3.20.

This example shows that the converse of Corollary 3.21 is not true

Example 3.22 Let $Y = \{0, c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5\}$ be a G -algebra in Remark 3.6 and $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^q, \lambda_{e_i}^q)$ is a neutrosophic soft cubic set defined by

	0	c_1	c_2	c_3	c_4	c_5
$A_{e_i}^T$	[0.3,0.5]	[0.3,0.4]	[0.3,0.4]	[0.3,0.4]	[0.1,0.2]	[0.1,0.2]
$A_{e_i}^I$	[0.5,0.7]	[0.2,0.3]	[0.2,0.3]	[0.5,0.7]	[0.1,0.1]	[0.1,0.1]
$A_{e_i}^F$	[0.4,0.6]	[0.2,0.5]	[0.2,0.5]	[0.2,0.5]	[0.1,0.2]	[0.1,0.2]

and

	0	c ₁	c ₂	c ₃	c ₄	c ₅
Λ ^T _{e_i}	0.1	0.4	0.4	0.6	0.4	0.6
Λ ^I _{e_i}	0.2	0.5	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.7
Λ ^F _{e_i}	0.3	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.6	0.8

We take $[w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}] = ([0.41, 0.48], [0.30, 0.36], [0.13, 0.17])$ and $t_{T,I,F_1} = (0.3, 0.4, 0.5)$. Then $A([w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}], t_{T,I,F_1}) = U(A_{e_i}^o | [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}]) \cap L(\lambda_{e_i}^o | t_{T,I,F_1}) = \{t_1 \in Y | A_{e_i}^o(t_1) \geq [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}], \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1) \leq t_{T,I,F_1}\} = \{0, c_1, c_2, c_3\} \cap \{0, c_1, c_2, c_4\} = \{0, c_1, c_2\}$ is a subalgebra of Y , but $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ is not a NSCSU, since $A_{e_i}^T(c_1 * c_3) = [0.2, 0.3] \not\geq [0.4, 0.5] = \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^T(c_1), A_{e_i}^T(c_3)\}$ and $\Lambda_{e_i}^T(c_2 * c_4) = 0.4 \not\leq 0.3 = \max\{\Lambda_{e_i}^T(c_2), \Lambda_{e_i}^T(c_4)\}$.

Theorem 3.23 Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ be a neutrosophic soft cubic set of Y , such that the sets $U(A_{e_i}^o | [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}])$ and $L(\lambda_{e_i}^o | t_{T,I,F_1})$ are subalgebras of Y for every $[w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}] \in D[0,1]$ and $t_{T,I,F_1} \in [0,1]$. Then $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ is NSCSU of Y .

Proof. Let $U(A_{e_i}^o | [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}])$ and $L(\lambda_{e_i}^o | t_{T,I,F_1})$ are subalgebras of Y for every $[w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}] \in D[0,1]$ and $t_{T,I,F_1} \in [0,1]$. On the contrary, let $(t_1)_0, (t_2)_0 \in Y$ be such that $A_{e_i}^o((t_1)_0 * (t_2)_0) < \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o((t_1)_0), A_{e_i}^o((t_2)_0)\}$. Let $A_{e_i}^o((t_1)_0) = [\phi_1, \phi_2]$, $A_{e_i}^o((t_2)_0) = [\phi_3, \phi_4]$ and $A_{e_i}^o((t_1)_0 * (t_2)_0) = [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}]$. Then $[w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}] < \text{rmin}\{[\phi_1, \phi_2], [\phi_3, \phi_4]\} = [\min\{\phi_1, \phi_3\}, \min\{\phi_2, \phi_4\}]$. So, $w_{T,I,F_1} < \text{rmin}\{\phi_1, \phi_3\}$ and $w_{T,I,F_2} < \min\{\phi_2, \phi_4\}$. Let us consider, $[\rho_1, \rho_2] = \frac{1}{2}[A_{e_i}^o((t_1)_0 * (t_2)_0) + \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o((t_1)_0), A_{e_i}^o((t_2)_0)\}] = \frac{1}{2}[[w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}] + [\min\{\phi_1, \phi_3\}, \min\{\phi_2, \phi_4\}]] = \frac{1}{2}(w_{T,I,F_1} + \min\{\phi_1, \phi_3\}), \frac{1}{2}(w_{T,I,F_2} + \min\{\phi_2, \phi_4\})$. Therefore, $\min\{\phi_1, \phi_3\} > \rho_1 = \frac{1}{2}(w_{T,I,F_1} + \min\{\phi_1, \phi_3\}) > w_{T,I,F_1}$ and $\min\{\phi_2, \phi_4\} > \rho_2 = \frac{1}{2}(w_{T,I,F_2} + \min\{\phi_2, \phi_4\}) > w_{T,I,F_2}$. Hence, $[\min\{\phi_1, \phi_3\}, \min\{\phi_2, \phi_4\}] > [\rho_1, \rho_2] > [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}]$ so that $(t_1)_0 * (t_2)_0 \notin U(A_{e_i}^o | [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}])$ which is a contradiction since $A_{e_i}^o((t_1)_0) = [\phi_1, \phi_2] \geq [\min\{\phi_1, \phi_3\}, \min\{\phi_2, \phi_4\}] > [\rho_1, \rho_2]$ and $A_{e_i}^o((t_2)_0) = [\phi_3, \phi_4] \geq [\min\{\phi_1, \phi_3\}, \min\{\phi_2, \phi_4\}] > [\rho_1, \rho_2]$. This implies $(t_1)_0 * (t_2)_0 \in U(A_{e_i}^o | [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}])$. Thus $A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in Y$.

Again, let $(t_1)_0, (t_2)_0 \in Y$ be such that $\lambda_{e_i}^o((t_1)_0 * (t_2)_0) > \max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o((t_1)_0), \lambda_{e_i}^o(0)\}$. Let $\lambda_{e_i}^o((t_1)_0) = \eta_{T,I,F_1}$, $\lambda_{e_i}^o((t_2)_0) = \eta_{T,I,F_2}$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o((t_1)_0 * (t_2)_0) = t_{T,I,F_1}$. Then $t_{T,I,F_1} > \max\{\zeta_{T,I,F_1}, \zeta_{T,I,F_2}\}$. Let us consider $t_{T,I,F_2} = \frac{1}{2}[\lambda_{e_i}^o((t_1)_0 * \hat{v}_0) + \max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o((t_1)_0), \lambda_{e_i}^o(0)\}]$. We get that $t_{T,I,F_2} = \frac{1}{2}(t_{T,I,F_1} + \max\{\zeta_{T,I,F_1}, \zeta_{T,I,F_2}\})$.

Therefore, $\zeta_{T,I,F_1} < t_{T,I,F_2} = \frac{1}{2}(t_{T,I,F_1} + \max\{\zeta_{T,I,F_1}, \zeta_{T,I,F_2}\}) < t_{T,I,F_1}$ and $\zeta_{T,I,F_2} < t_{T,I,F_2} = \frac{1}{2}(t_{T,I,F_1} + \max\{\zeta_{T,I,F_1}, \zeta_{T,I,F_2}\}) < t_{T,I,F_1}$. Hence, $\max\{\zeta_{T,I,F_1}, \zeta_{T,I,F_2}\} < t_{T,I,F_2} < t_{T,I,F_1} = \lambda_{e_i}^o((t_1)_0, (t_2)_0)$, so that $(t_1)_0 * (t_2)_0 \notin L(\lambda_{e_i}^o | t_{T,I,F_1})$ which is a contradiction since $\lambda_{e_i}^o((t_1)_0) = \zeta_{T,I,F_1} \leq \max\{\zeta_{T,I,F_1}, \zeta_{T,I,F_2}\} < t_{T,I,F_2}$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o((t_2)_0) = \zeta_{T,I,F_2} \leq \max\{\zeta_{T,I,F_1}, \zeta_{T,I,F_2}\} < t_{T,I,F_2}$. This implies $(t_1)_0, (t_2)_0 \in L(\lambda_{e_i}^o | t_{T,I,F_1})$. Thus $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in Y$.

$t_2) \leq \max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in Y$. Therefore, $U(A_{e_i}^o | [w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}])$ and $L(\lambda_{e_i}^o | t_{T,I,F_1})$ are subalgebras of Y . Hence, $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ is NSCSU of Y .

Theorem 3.24 Any subalgebra of Y can be consider as both the upper $[w_{T,I,F_1}, w_{T,I,F_2}]$ - level and lower t_{T,I,F_1} -level of some NSCSU of Y .

Proof. Let $\tilde{\mathcal{N}}_k$ be a NSCSU of Y , and $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ be a neutrosophic soft cubic set on Y defined by

$$A_{e_i}^o = \begin{cases} [\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}] & \text{if } t_1 \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_k \\ [0,0] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \lambda_{e_i}^o = \begin{cases} \beta_{T,I,F_1} & \text{if } t_1 \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_k \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}.$$

$\forall [\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}] \in D[0,1]$ and $\beta_{T,I,F_1} \in [0,1]$. We consider the following cases.

Case1 : If $\forall t_1, t_2 \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_k$ then $A_{e_i}^o(t_1) = [\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}]$, $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1) = \beta_{T,I,F_1}$ and $A_{e_i}^o(t_2) = [\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}]$, $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2) = \beta_{T,I,F_1}$. Thus $A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) = [\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}] = \text{rmin}\{[\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}], [\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}]\} = \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) = \beta_{T,I,F_1} = \max\{\beta_{T,I,F_1}, \beta_{T,I,F_1}\} = \max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$.

Case2: If $t_1 \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_k$ and $t_2 \notin \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_k$, then $A_{e_i}^o(t_1) = [\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}]$, $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1) = \beta_{T,I,F_1}$ and $A_{e_i}^o(t_2) = [0,0]$, $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2) = 1$. Thus $A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \geq [0,0] = \text{rmin}\{[\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}], [0,0]\} = \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \leq 1 = \max\{\beta_{T,I,F_1}, 1\} = \max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$.

Case3 : If $t_1 \notin \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_k$ and $t_2 \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_k$, then $A_{e_i}^o(t_1) = [0,0]$, $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1) = 1$ and $A_{e_i}^o(t_2) = [\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}]$, $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2) = \beta_{T,I,F_1}$. Thus $A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \geq [0,0] = \text{rmin}\{[0,0], [\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}]\} = \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \leq 1 = \max\{1, \beta_{T,I,F_1}\} = \max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$.

Case4: If $t_1 \notin \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_k$ and $t_2 \notin \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_k$, then $A_{e_i}^o(t_1) = [0,0]$, $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1) = 1$ and $A_{e_i}^o(t_2) = [0,0]$, $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2) = 1$. Thus $A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \geq [0,0] = \text{rmin}\{[0,0], [0,0]\} = \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \leq 1 = \max\{1, 1\} = \max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}$. Therefore, $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is a NSCSU of Y .

Theorem 3.25 Let $\tilde{\mathcal{N}}_k$ be a subset of Y and $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ be a neutrosophic soft cubic set on Y which is given in the proof of Theorem 3.24. If $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is realized as lower level subalgebra and upper level subalgebra of some NSCSU of Y , then $\tilde{\mathcal{N}}_k$ is a neutrosophic soft cubic one of Y .

Proof. Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ be a NSCSU of Y , and $t_1, t_2 \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_k$. Then $A_{e_i}^o(t_1) = A_{e_i}^o(t_2) = [\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}]$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1) = \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2) = \beta_{T,I,F_1}$. Thus $A_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} = \text{rmin}\{[\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}], [\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}]\} = [\xi_{T,I,F_1}, \xi_{T,I,F_2}]$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} = \max\{\beta_{T,I,F_1}, \beta_{T,I,F_1}\} = \beta_{T,I,F_1} \Rightarrow t_1 * t_2 \in \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_k$. Hence $\tilde{\mathcal{N}}_k$ is a neutrosophic soft cubic one of Y .

4 Homomorphism of Neutrosophic Soft Cubic Subalgebras

Suppose τ be a mapping from a set Y into a set Y and $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ be a neutrosophic soft cubic set in Y . Then the inverse-image of $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is defined as $\tau^{-1}(\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k) = \{(t_1, \tau^{-1}(A_{e_i}^o), \tau^{-1}(\lambda_{e_i}^o)) | t_1 \in Y\}$ and $\tau^{-1}(A_{e_i}^o)(t_1) = A_{e_i}^o(\tau(t_1))$ and $\tau^{-1}(\lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_1) = \lambda_{e_i}^o(\tau(t_1))$. It is clear that $\tau^{-1}(\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k)$ is a neutrosophic soft cubic set.

Theorem 4.1 Let $\tau | Y \rightarrow X$ is a homomorphic mapping of G -algebra. If $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ is a NSCSU of X . Then the pre-image $\tau^{-1}(\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k) = \{(t_1, \tau^{-1}(A_{e_i}^o), \tau^{-1}(\lambda_{e_i}^o)) | t_1 \in X\}$ of $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ under τ is a NSCSU of Y .

Proof. Assume that $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ is a NSCSU of Y and $t_1, t_2 \in Y$. Then $\tau^{-1}(A_{e_i}^o)(t_1 * t_2) = A_{e_i}^o(\tau(t_1 * t_2)) = A_{e_i}^o(\tau(t_1) * \tau(t_2)) \geq \text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(\tau(t_1)), A_{e_i}^o(\tau(t_2))\} = \text{rmin}\{\tau^{-1}(A_{e_i}^o)(t_1), \tau^{-1}(A_{e_i}^o)(t_2)\}$ and $\tau^{-1}(\lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_1 * t_2) = \lambda_{e_i}^o(\tau(t_1 * t_2)) = \lambda_{e_i}^o(\tau(t_1) * \tau(t_2)) \leq \max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(\tau(t_1)), \lambda_{e_i}^o(\tau(t_2))\} = \max\{\tau^{-1}(\lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_1), \tau^{-1}(\lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_2)\}$. Hence $\tau^{-1}(\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k) = \{(t_1, \tau^{-1}(A_{e_i}^o), \tau^{-1}(\lambda_{e_i}^o)) | t_1 \in Y\}$ is NSCSU of Y .

Theorem 4.2 Let $\tau | Y \rightarrow X$ is a homomorphic mapping of G -algebra and $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_j}^o, \lambda_{e_j}^o)$ is a NSCSU of X where $j \in k$. If $\inf\{\max\{\lambda_{e_j}^o(t_2), \lambda_{e_j}^o(t_2)\}\} = \max\{\inf \lambda_{e_j}^o(t_2), \inf \lambda_{e_j}^o(t_2)\} \quad \forall t_2 \in Y$. Then $\tau^{-1}(\bigcap_{j \in k} \tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k)$ is a NSCSU of Y .

Proof. Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_j}^o, \lambda_{e_j}^o)$ be a NSCSU of Y where $j \in k$ satisfying $\inf\{\max\{\lambda_{e_j}^o(t_2), \lambda_{e_j}^o(t_2)\}\} = \max\{\inf \lambda_{e_j}^o(t_2), \inf \lambda_{e_j}^o(t_2)\} \quad \forall t_2 \in Y$. Then by Theorem 3.8, $\bigcap_{j \in k} \tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is a

NSCSU of Y . Hence $\tau^{-1}(\bigcap_{j \in k} \tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k)$ is also a NSCSU of Y .

Definition 4.3 A neutrosophic soft cubic set $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ in Y is said to have sup-property and inf-property if for any subset S of Y , $\exists s_0 \in T$ such that $A_{e_i}^o(s_0) = \text{rsup}_{s_0 \in S} A_{e_i}^o(s_0)$ and $\lambda_{e_i}^o(s_0) = \inf_{t_0 \in T} \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_0)$ respectively.

Definition 4.4 Let τ be the mapping from the set Y to the set X . If $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ is neutrosophic cubic set of Y , then the image of $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ under τ denoted by $\tau(\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k)$ and is defined as $\tau(\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k) = \{(t_1, \tau_{\text{rsup}}(A_{e_i}^o), \tau_{\text{inf}}(\lambda_{e_i}^o)) | t_1 \in Y\}$, where

$$\tau_{\text{rsup}}(A_{e_i}^o)(t_2) = \begin{cases} A_{e_i}^o(t_1), & \text{if } \tau^{-1}(t_2) \neq \phi \\ t_1 \in \tau^{-1}(t_2) \\ [0,0], & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

and

$$\tau_{\text{inf}}(\lambda_{e_i}^o)(t_2) = \begin{cases} \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), & \text{if } \tau^{-1}(t_2) \neq \phi \\ t_1 \in \tau^{-1}(t_2) \\ 1, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Theorem 4.5 Assume $\tau | Y \rightarrow X$ is a homomorphic mapping of G - algebra and $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ is a NSCSU of Y , where $i \in k$. If $\inf\{\max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1)\}\} = \max\{\inf \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \inf \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1)\} \quad \forall t_1 \in Y$. Then $\tau(\bigcap_{i \in k} \tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k)$ is a NSCSU of Y .

Proof. Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ be NSCSU of Y where $i \in k$ satisfying $\inf\{\max\{\lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1)\}\} = \max\{\inf \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1), \inf \lambda_{e_i}^o(t_1)\} \quad \forall t_1 \in Y$. Then by Theorem 3.8, $\bigcap_{i \in k} \tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is a NSCSU of Y . Hence $\tau(\bigcap_{i \in k} \tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k)$ is a NSCSU of Y .

Theorem 4.6 Suppose $\tau | Y \rightarrow X$ is a homomorphic mapping of G -algebra. Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ be NSCSU of Y where $i \in k$. If $\text{rsup}\{\text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}\} = \text{rmin}\{\text{rsup} A_{e_i}^o(t_1), \text{rsup} A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} \quad \forall t_1, t_2 \in X$. Then $\tau(\bigcup_{i \in k} \tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k)$ is a NSCSU of X .

Proof. Let $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k = (A_{e_i}^o, \lambda_{e_i}^o)$ be NSCSU of Y where $i \in k$ satisfying $\text{rsup}\{\text{rmin}\{A_{e_i}^o(t_1), A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\}\} = \text{rmin}\{\text{rsup}A_{e_i}^o(t_1), \text{rsup}A_{e_i}^o(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in Y$. Then by Theorem 3.8, $\bigcup_{i \in k} \tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is a NSCSU of Y . Hence $\tau(\bigcup_{i \in k} \tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k)$ is a NSCSU of X .

Corollary 4.7 For a homomorphism $\tau | Y \rightarrow X$ of G -algebras, these results hold:

1. If $\forall i \in k, \tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ are NSCSU of Y , then $\tau(\bigcap_{i \in k} (\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k))$ is NSCSU of X
2. If $\forall i \in k, \tilde{\mathcal{N}}_k$ are NSCSU of X , then $\tau^{-1}(\bigcap_{i \in k} (\tilde{\mathcal{N}}_k))$ is NSCSU of Y .

Proof. Straightforward.

Theorem 4.8 Let τ be an isomorphic mapping from a G -algebra Y to a G -algebra X . If $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$ is a NSCSU of Y . Then $\tau^{-1}(\tau(\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k)) = \tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$.

Proof. For any $t_1 \in Y$, let $\tau(t_1) = t_2$. Since τ is an isomorphism, $\tau^{-1}(t_2) = \{t_1\}$. Thus $\tau(\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k)(\tau(t_1)) = \tau(\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k)(t_2) = \bigcup_{t_1 \in \tau^{-1}(t_2)} \tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k(t_1) = \tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k(t_1)$. For any $t_2 \in Y$, since τ is an isomorphism, $\tau^{-1}(t_2) = \{t_1\}$ so that $\tau(t_1) = t_2$. Thus $\tau^{-1}(\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k)(t_1) = \tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k(\tau(t_1)) = \tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k(t_2)$. Hence, $\tau^{-1}(\tau(\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k)) = \tau^{-1}(\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k) = \tilde{\mathcal{P}}_k$.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, the concept of neutrosophic soft cubic subalgebra of G -algebra was investigated through several useful results. Homomorphc properties of NSCSU were also investigated. For future work this study will provide base for t -soft cubic subalgebra, t -neutrosophic soft cubic subalgebra.

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